

MICRO RNA MODULATION FOR NUCLEUS PULPOSUS REGENERATION IN THE INTERVERTEBRAL DISC

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INTRODUCTION

Lower back pain is a global epidemiological and socioeconomic problem affecting up to 80% of people at some stage during their life and is believed to be due to degeneration of the intervertebral disc (IVD) [1]. Early-stage disc degeneration begins with a loss of glycosaminoglycans (GAGs) from the central part of the disc known as the nucleus pulposus (NP). Diminished GAG content leads to a loss in the ability to absorb compressive loads resulting in reduced disc height and can lead to nerve compression and pain [2]. The use of microRNAs (miRs) to improve tissue regeneration has gained traction as a method of delivering therapeutic nucleic acids without the drawbacks of previously attempted trials using growth factors, which has associated limitations of short half-life and the need for repeat injections [3]. This study will examine the potency of employing miR-140, miR-149, and miR-221, all identified in the literature as having the potential to modulate the degradation of the IVD and help stimulate rejuvenation of the NP cell phenotype. Non-viral cell penetrating peptides (CPPs), including cationic 30 mer amphipathic peptide (RALA) and GAG-binding enhanced transduction FGF2B-LK15-8R (GET-FLR) [5] will be investigated to identify the most efficacious delivery vector for miR complexation and transfection of NP cells, with Lipofectamine RNAiMAX [6] serving as a positive control. The aim of this study is to transfect primary rat NP cells using these carrier-miR complexes over a period of 14 days to modulate anabolic/catabolic gene and protein expression. The extent of modulation in primary NP cells will be determined using cell viability assays and immunohistochemistry. Optimisation of miR concentration to elicit a response will also be performed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Rat NP cells will be isolated from donors following euthanasia and digested for 6 hours with collagenase type II (1.5mg/ml) and pronase (1mg/ml) and culture expanded (passage 3). Carrier-miR complexes will be prepared for RALA, GET-FLR, and Lipofectamine RNAiMAX for N/P ratios of 10, 5, and 2.72, respectively. NP cells will be transfected with respective carrier-miR complexes and seeded into well plates at a density of 20,000 cells per well. Analysis of cell viability and immunohistochemistry will be performed at days 3, 7, and 14, employing well-established markers of IVD

degeneration, namely *ADAMTS-4*, *COL2A1*, *ACAN*, *MMP3* & *SOX9*.

EXPECTED RESULTS

It is hypothesised that miR transfection will modulate the expression of key NP degeneration and regeneration proteins in this 2D model.

Figure 1 Workflow for carrier-miR complexation, transfection, and analysis in rat NP cells. Created with BioRender.com

DISCUSSION

This initial study will provide a framework to develop high-throughput in vitro experiments, enabling comparison of the functionality and potential therapeutic capabilities of miRs for NP cell regeneration. This foundation will enable the progression to 3D culture models, culminating with in vivo studies to better elucidate potential strategies of stimulating regeneration of resident NP cells in the IVD towards developing minimally invasive injectable therapeutics utilising miR platform technology.

REFERENCES

- [1] Dieleman *et al*, JAMA, 316(24): 2627-2646, 2016
- [2] Adams *et al*, Clin Biomech (Bristol, Avon), 25(10): 961-71, 2010
- [3] Tsekoura *et al*, ACS Biomater Sci Eng., 3(7): 1195-1206, 2016
- [4] Raftery *et al*, Biomaterials, 216: 119277, 2019
- [5] Blokpoel *et al*, ACS Appl. Nano Mater, 4, 167-181, 2021
- [6] Cardarelli *et al*, Scientific Reports 6, 2016

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